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Prediction of School Safety Awareness through Social Media, Self-Efficacy and Parental Socio-economic Status among Secondary School Students in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The importance of school safety awareness is within the purview of avoidance or mitigate the occurrences of school violence and insecurities. Extant studies focused not on the independent variables used. The purpose of this study is to predict school safety awareness through social media, self-efficacy and parental socio-economic status. The target population consists all secondary school students with age range of 13 years and above. A simple random sampling technique was used for the study. The instruments used were School Safety ($\alpha = .91$), Social Media ($\alpha = .84$), and Self-Efficacy ($\alpha = .76$) scales. Data were analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation, Multiple Regression Analyses. Findings showed that there is positive significant relationship between independent variables and school safety awareness, social media ($r = .523$); self-efficacy ($r = .367$); and parental socio-economic status ($r = .241$). Furthermore, the significance of composite contribution showed the analysis of variance of the regression with significant while the relative contribution revealed the self-efficacy as the most potent factor in the prediction of school safety awareness. Therefore, it was recommended that provision for school security should be put in place by government in support of stakeholders, parents, school management in enhancing school safety awareness and reducing school problems.

Keyword: School safety awareness, social media, self-efficacy, parental socioeconomic status, Secondary school students

Introduction

School safety awareness is an integral aspect of school efficiency and security precautions of violence and other school problems such as bullying, truancy, dropout, academic failure and suicide in which schools and students do not take safety into consideration to the need for prevention and preparation as mandatory responsibilities. Keeping safe and avoiding risks to students at schools are obviously important issues for building capacity, attainment intellectual capability and national development that concerned people should take note. Generally, no one wants their lives to be temporarily or permanently affected by bad learning or working conditions. However, Abdullah and Abd-Aziz (2020) emphasise that safety awareness should be developed to the highest level possible to foster a healthy and safe environment for all students.

As a student or teacher, one needs to be aware of issues that may affect health and safety at school. Although, it is up to school management and other government agencies to make sure that any potential risk to school safety are properly controlled, also, need to be aware of school safety awareness are the responsibilities of both students, teachers, management and others (Hakimi, 2014). A safe school is an enabling and conducive environment for teaching, training and learning that free from physical threats and danger emanating from inside or outside the school premises. Safety awareness among school students is fundamental to preventing injuries and illnesses (Kadir, 2020). A low level of safety awareness can affect the high rate of accidents. Accident rates can also be reduced in the ways students comply with essential aspects of school safety rules by increasing safety awareness (Mardziah, 2022). The same thing was also stated by Abdullah et al. (2021) that

students' commitment if they comply with safety practices could increase their awareness towards good safety. Therefore, safety awareness must continually be improved and be avoided at high rate of compliance with safety awareness among students.

The school is a knowledge-building state where body of knowledge requires a safety environment to attain its full plight of academic aims, objectives, vision, mission, and achievement. The saying that 'safety and learning shake hand-in-hand' explains the interrelationship of safety with education. This assertion generally means that safety is crucial to students' well-being and learning. A safe school is a place where teachers and students can get a high quality education without threat of violence. Thus, creating and maintaining a safe school environment is a vision shared by all schools. The lack of school safety awareness, regulations, enforcement agencies, and facilities drastically hampered the identification, location, and hence control of the serious hazards that existed, and the resultant injuries and illnesses to learning processing and learning outcomes (Abubakar, 2022).

According to the United Nations, the protracted nature of conflicts as induced by educational goals and means keeps affecting the future of entire generations of children. In effect, occurrences of the scourge of banditry, kidnapping, rape, suicide, and the likes as being experienced in schools are becoming rampant so much that it dominates public debates and outcry (Ngoka, et. al. 2020). This is of concern to scholars and stakeholders concerns and call for immediate intervention by scholars, researcher, non-government amongst others. A report by the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) had it that, not less than 87 countries are reported to have case of attacks on education between year 2014 and 2018 (UNICEF, 2020). Therefore, school safety awareness is the task of educating the school community to integrate school safety into the education agenda.

School safety awareness is concerned with the acquisition of experience through garnering and practicing safety skills and measures. Despite the contemporary development in learning sources and the variety of its means, safety awareness is the heart of school safety. It is an integral aspect of school efficiency where students are the significant stakeholders in the school where awareness of safety and security precautions means a lot to the concept of efficiency (Kipngeno, 2019). While awareness of the links between safety and violence and other school problems, such as bullying, suicide, truancy and dropout rates, and academic failure are well ascertained, many school students do not connect safety to need for prevention and preparation as their responsibility. Invariably, the importance of school safety awareness is within the purview to avoid or mitigate the occurrences of school violence or insecurities. A school must organise and form its team; parents, teacher, school, psychologist, security personnel, students' leaders, etc. have the same vision and mindset that safety is the main factor in achieving academic excellence amongst students.

According to the United Nations, as of 2019, about 1.8 million people have been displaced. Most importantly, their campaign against Western Education has seen many schools attacked, burnt and many workers killed. Statistically, from the year 2009 to 2018, no less than 600 teachers were killed, 910 schools damaged or destroyed and more than 1,500 schools forced to close due to armed group related violence, interrupting the schooling of more than 900,000 children. In 2018, an estimated 432 children were reported to have been maimed, while *Boko Haram* also abducted 180 children, many of whom are girls, for recruitment, sexual abuse, forced marriage, or as carriers of improvised explosive devices (IEDs) Global Coalition to Protect Education from Attack, 2020). According to Aremu (2021), terrorism and armed banditry are not the only rhetoric associated with schools in recent times, and in the interview, the occasional abductions are gradually growing into full scale occupation in Nigeria. This is even more worrisome with the fact that such alarming conditions are gaining momentum beyond the shores of the northern part of the country and towards the south.

Nigeria is fast becoming a hub for terrorism in Africa, one of the countries with the deadliest extremist armed groups in the world. The *Boko Haram* and *banditry* grip of some parts of the northern state is over a decade, and with dastardly records of perpetrated conflict and violent activity over the years. The result of these has seen scores of individuals either been killed or displaced from their place of domicile. In recent times, the Nigerian secondary school system is under continuous and recurring violent attacks by bandits and terrorists, especially in the northern part of the country. While this has become an almost weekly recurrence in the schools in the north, schools in other parts of the country are not exempted from bandits' attacks leading to the abductions of hundreds of secondary school students. In many cases, these students are kept for weeks and months and ransoms in money and materials (including foodstuffs) paid by state governments, parents, and guardians. Media is a phenomenon of the digital age, affirming itself as a powerful mechanism that can open space for vast opportunities for collaborative communication (Kaplan, 2025). The tools used by social media are based on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and enable the creation and exchange of user-generated content has been a revolutionary development for corporations and individuals Applications such as Twitter, Instagram or Four square, which did not even exist a decade ago, form an essential part of today's media and communication landscape. Social media, it

means "to allow conversations". They are web sites built to allow social interaction and information sharing in various formats: photos, messages, icons, and more.

Therefore, Social media can be broadly defined as the set of interactive Internet applications that facilitate (collaborative or individual) creation, and sharing of user-generated content. Examples of social media platforms are numerous and varied. They include Facebook, Friendster, Wikipedia, dating sites, Craigslist, recipe sharing sites (e.g. all-recipes.com), YouTube, and Instagram. Social media platforms all share the above-mentioned characteristics, but are unique from one another in many respects. In particular, platforms often vary in their architectures, structures, norms, and user bases (Perassi and Meneghel, 2021).

Statement of the problem

Safety awareness, regrettably, there has not been sufficient academic attention, especially as regards means of improving safety awareness in secondary schools. A high point among the phenomenon of school security is the improper and lack of awareness of school safety procedures among students. More importantly, efforts at fostering security awareness or safety in school are focused on addressing the physical aspect of school safety through the provision and procedural use of circuit television system (CCTV), high fences, and presence of uniformed security personnel to curb school insecurity, not much have been affected in the sphere of psychological interventions.

While these go on unabated and uncensored, the attendant emotional traumas, agonies, physical bruises, hunger, and dehumanization of the abducted students; and those experienced by the parents/guardians, school management and personnel and other concerned stakeholders are better imagined than feeling them. Abducted students have also reported experiencing mental health and psychological challenges and may also develop a cold attitude to schooling after their release from kidnappers. Given these concerns, this study will ascertain the influence of social media, self-efficacy and socio-economic status on school safety awareness among secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The study sought to:

- ascertain the significant relationship between social media, self-efficacy, socio-economic status and school safety awareness among secondary school students
- determine the composite effect of independent variables on school safety awareness among secondary school students
- reveal the potent relative prediction of independent variables on school safety awareness among secondary school students

Research Questions

R₁: What is the significant relationship between social media, self-efficacy, socio-economic status and school safety awareness among secondary school students?

R₂: What is the composite effect of independent variables on school safety awareness among secondary school students?

R₃: What are the potent relative prediction of independent variables on school safety awareness among secondary school students?

Literature Review

The physical school environment encompasses the school building and other contents that include infrastructure, furniture and presence of chemical and biological equipment; community; and the surrounding environment with which children may come into contact, as well as nearby land, uses, roadways and other hazards (World Health Organisation, 2024). A positive school safety should take cognizance of reasonable physical security such as locked doors, lighted hallways, main gate and security, and visitor check-in system among others. On the other hand, schools must ensure the psychological safety i.e. emotional stability, school connectedness, positive learning readiness and intention of students as well as other psychological wellbeing. This is important from the point of need to build students' resilience and ability to cope or act when a crisis does occur in any setting.

Therefore, the need to expose students to risk management, safety practices, first aid etc. Mitigation of crimes, terrorism, and hazards requires sets of measures, including applying school training using personal safety skills. School administration preparation programs are an important aspect of school safety awareness as well as of forming an outcome of knowledge skills which prepares the students who are primary targets of school insecurity with risk management and dealing properly with emergency situations in the school environment. However, the importance of a common framework allows roles and

responsibilities to be assigned to everyone and develops an effective network of coordinated emergency management by every educational stakeholder. Unfortunately, the lack of school safety awareness and vision jeopardizes the readiness and capacity of many schools to respond and act when confronted by insecurity.

Meanwhile, Ubom and Joshua (2024) observed that teachers are no doubt, the heart of any school system. They are looked forward to in the attainment of reasonable level of productivity, thus, their employers demand from them some level of faithfulness, support, and job engagement. In order to be productive, there is therefore, the need for them to be adequately motivated. One of the ways by which this could be achieved is by ensuring the safety of the school.

Roberts, Kemp, Rathbun & Morgan (2024) opined that every school safety programme should put the following measures into consideration:

- **Technology:** it includes security cameras, and other technologically-aided devices which can be effectively utilized by strategically locating them, with competent personnel assigned to handle them.
- **Profession:** aim of using trained security personnel who will ensure compliance with the laid down rules and regulations, as well as providing enlightenment and guidance for staff and students should be put in place;
- Training on school safety for staff and students;
- Non-violence intervention which involves instituting measures that address hostile behaviours among teachers, students, and their parents; and
- Parents' responsibilities which have to do with the involvement of parents by creating awareness which could be done during the meetings of the Parents' Forum.

In order to locate, organize, structure and classify the conceptual results of social media, the method of Systematic Review (RS) of the literature was adopted for the course of the research, since RS is an explicit (comprehensive) method and reproducible to identify, evaluate and synthesize the existing body of completed and recorded works produced by researchers and scholars (Freitas, 2019).

Social media, begins with the term media, "support, the vehicle or communication channel, through which information can be conducted, distributed or disseminated, as a" means "of communication" Freitas (2019) in this sense even the human body can be considered a media that has the potential to inform and communicate something. What differs from social media of other communication and information technologies is the possibility for the user to expose content in a public way and through this to be able to create ties with other users that have common interest. Thus facilitating the dissemination and sharing of knowledge. In this context, social media can act as instruments or as technological agents (Kaplan, 2025).

Currently, there are around 2.62 billion social media users worldwide, with this number rising each year. This figure contains all age groups, including young people who are particularly involved with social media. Sites such as Facebook and Twitter are popular among adults and young people alike, whereas apps like Snapchat and Instagram are largely favoured by the younger generations. Social media is now considered the most popular method of communication among teens and one of their main ways of socialising. This social media popularity among teens, however, is accompanied by potential dangers. The risk of interacting with groomers and being exposed to radicalisation exists across many online platforms. This makes it crucial to teach young people how to stay safe on social media so they can get the most out of the online world. Schools are a great place to raise this awareness as students can learn interactively with their peers and explore the positives and negatives of social media in context.

Self-efficacy refers to students' belief in their ability to succeed in specific situations or accomplish a task. It's a crucial concept in psychology, education, and motivation. It's not about having high self-esteem or simply believing you're capable, but rather a judgment of one's capabilities in a specific domain or situation. Recent research emphasizes the domain-specific nature of self-efficacy, meaning that someone might have high self-efficacy in one area (like academics) but low self-efficacy in another (like public speaking). By understanding self-efficacy, individuals can take steps to develop their confidence and abilities, leading to greater success and achievement.

Snell, Bailey, Carona, and Mebane (2022) in a study on security and safety measures in American Public Schools, found out that the rate of keeping illicit drugs among students reduced to four percent in 2001 and the rate of physical attacks on members of staff also reduced to 16 percent in 2001. Similarly, from 1995 to 2001, the reported cases of unfair treatment and exploitative acts reduced from 10 percent to 6 percent. A safe school provides opportunities for students to learn to the best of their abilities, for teachers to operate under the conditions that encourage transformation and novel ideas, and for increasing and strengthening the administrative abilities and potentials of institutional leaders. This is due to the fact that proficient, knowledgeable, and conscientious employees are desirous of providing services under that condition (Igwagu, 2016).

Social media use permeates all facets of daily life, so it's no surprise that school safety has been massively influenced by what students post online. With 97% of teenagers going online daily and 46% stating that they are online constantly, social media platforms have become a hotbed for the spreading and identifying of threats. Prinsloo (2023) argued that a safe school is indispensable in the achievement of functional educative process because, a secure and hitch-free school is one which is visibly as well as psychologically invulnerable, thereby allowing teachers, and other staff to render services unhindered and without any fear of attacks.

One of the main challenges that schools face is the prevalence of cyber aggression. Between 9% and 35% of young people are victims of cyber aggression, while between 4% and 21% are perpetrators. Additionally, 14.8% of students have reported being electronically bullied via email, chat rooms, instant messaging, websites, or texting. While cyberbullying is nominal compared to the scope of threats at school, instances of cyberbullying are most important to the context of a student's behavioral patterns and must be investigated in the threat assessment process. It is however, logical to submit that the teachers' ability to cater for the well-beings of the learners will be dependent on the extent to which he himself is secured within the school. Kim and Jung (2019) found that self-efficacy has been proposed to significantly and positively correlate with safety awareness.

Methodology

This study uses a quantitative approach through the survey method. A set of questionnaires has been created to obtain information related to safety awareness among students. The population of this study comprises of public secondary school students in Oyo State. The study used simple random sampling techniques to select three hundred and fifty (350) public secondary school students. These schools were selected due to localization.

Instrumentation

The questionnaire used in the study was adapted and adopted instruments developed to elicit information from the respondents and was tagged (SSMGES). The questionnaire comprises of items each rated on 4-Likert point format ranging from 4= SA to 1=SD. Examples of the items are: "My School promotes safety awareness and preparedness; Social networks are a great way for people to stay in touch with one another; If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways to get what I want.". However, the instruments were validated and new reliability coefficient of; School Safety Awareness Scale ($r=.86$), Social Media Scale ($r=.77$), General Self-Efficacy Scale ($r=.69$) were obtained using Cronbach alpha.

Data Analysis

Data were collected, collated and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools with aid of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS, IBM 20 Version). Descriptive statistic of frequency distribution and simple percent was used for demographic information while inferential statistical tool of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Regression Analysis was used to answer research questions 1 to 3 at 0.05 level of significance.

Result

Respondents' Demographic Information

Result reveals that out of 350 respondents used in the study, 171 (48.86%) of the respondents are males while 179 (49.72%) of the respondents are females, it means females respondents are more than males respondents. Out of 350 respondents, 86 (24.57%) of the respondents are below 11 years, 168 (48.00%) of the respondents are 12-14 year interval, 94 (26.86%) of the respondents are 13-15 years' interval while 2 (0.57%) of the respondents are 16 years and above interval. 121 (34.57%) of the respondents are under low socio-economic status, 145 (41.43%) of the respondents are medium socio-economic status, while 84 (24.0%) of the respondents are belong to high socio-economic status as categorized in the study.

Research Question One

R₁: What is the significant relationship between social media, self-efficacy, socio-economic status and school safety awareness among secondary school students?

Table 1: Summary of correlation matrix showing the relationship between the study variables

Scientific Table	1	2	3	4	Mean \bar{x}	SD
School Safety Awareness	1.000				78.50	13.60
Social Media	.523**	1.000			70.29	18.31
Self-efficacy	.367**	.519**	1.000		145.83	39.17
Socio-economic Status	.241**	.427**	.156**	1.000	31.60	5.48

Source: Field Survey

Table 1 reveals the inter-correlation matrix of the independent variables (social media, self-efficacy and socio-economic status) on the dependent variable (school safety awareness) among secondary school students. All the three factors are positively correlated with school safety awareness among secondary school students in which social media ($r = .523, p < 0.05$) had significant relationship to school safety awareness, self-efficacy ($r = .367, p < 0.05$) had significant relationship to school safety awareness, and socio-economic status ($r = .241, p < 0.05$) had significant relationship to school safety awareness. This implies that social media, self-efficacy and socio-economic status play a crucial impact on school safety awareness among public secondary school.

Research Question 2: What is the composite effect of independent variables on school safety awareness among secondary school students?

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis on School Safety Awareness

Multiple R= .469					
Multiple R ² = .358					
Multiple R ² (adjusted)=.297					
Standard error of estimate= 8.37471					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	756.087	3	252.029	.741	.017 ^b
Residual	64595.815	346	186.693		
Total	65,351.92	349			

Source: Field Survey

The table 2 shows the combined influence of the independent variables (social media, self-efficacy and socio-economic status) on the dependent variable (school safety awareness) among secondary school students Oyo State, Nigeria. The value of $R = .467$, while $R^2 = .358$. This suggests that all the three factors combined together accounted for ($Adj.R^2 = .297$) variance in the prediction of school safety awareness. The other factors accounting for the remaining percentage variance in the prediction of school safety awareness beyond the scope of this study. The ANOVA result from the regression analysis indicates that there was a significant influence of the independent variables (social media, self-efficacy and socio-economic status) on school safety awareness, $F(.741, p < 0.05)$ among secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3: What are the potent relative prediction of independent variables on school safety awareness among secondary school students?

Table 3: Relative influence of each of the independent factors to the prediction of school safety awareness among secondary school students

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	95.391	8.726		10.932	.000
Self-efficacy	.315	.163	.310	1.932	.000
Social media	.198	.118	.115	1.678	.000
Socio-economic Status	.148	.126	.104	1.175	.203

Source: Field Survey

The table 3 revealed the relative influence of each of the independent variables (social media, self-efficacy, and socio-economic status) to the dependent variable (school safety awareness) among secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria; social media ($\beta = .310, p < 0.05$) had significant relative influence to school safety awareness followed social media ($\beta = .115, p < 0.05$) had significant relative influence to school safety awareness followed by socio-economic status ($\beta = .104, p < 0.05$) had significant relative influence to school safety awareness among secondary school students. In term of magnitude of influence, self-efficacy made the most significant influence to school safety awareness among secondary school students in Ibadan, Nigeria, followed by self-efficacy, and socio-economic status respectively.

Discussion of findings

It was found that social media has significant impact in boosting school safety awareness among secondary school students. However, social media found to improve and hinder school safety awareness base on the usage and level of exposure of the media among secondary school students. On one hand, it can be used to quickly disseminate important information and promote safe practices, but it can also be a source of misinformation and distractions that detract from focus on safety. The finding of this study is agreed with the study of Prinsloo (2023) who found out that social media and school safety awareness amongst students showed a positive significant relationship when compared the two variables. In meta-analysis study carried out by Snell, et. al (2022) found the positive impact of social media on creating good school safety awareness in high school students and the workers. Hence, the role of social media could not be overemphasis when creating a solid awareness of school safety.

In another research question that stated the relationship between self-efficacy and safety awareness among secondary school students. It was found that there was significant positive relationship existing between self-efficacy and safety awareness among secondary school students. This implies that self-efficacy justified the rate of safety awareness in school and prompt good characters and enhancing betterment of academic learning outcome. This is in support of a study conducted by Adjekum (2017) and Kim & ung (2019) who they found that self-efficacy has been proposed to significantly and positively correlate with safety awareness. the study further that Workers with a high level of self-efficacy show more initiative at work and are more willing to learn new skills, making more efforts to understand safety procedures as well as learning skills that are necessary for them to do their work safely (Chughtai, 2015), which may increase their awareness and ability to perform safety compliance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It was concluded based on the finding of this current study that self-efficacy, socio media and socio-economic status play a significant role in shaping secondary school student behaviors safety outcomes. In the context of school safety, students with higher self-efficacy may be more likely to take proactive steps to ensure their safety and the safety of others in the school while social media served as a tool for promoting awareness and providing support, but it may also contribute to increased feelings of loneliness and decreased self-efficacy in some students based on this finding of this study likewise, Socio-economic status shows a significant predictor of access to resources and opportunities to create good safety awareness

in the school system irrespective of parental socio-economic status. In the context of school safety, students from lower socio-economic backgrounds may face unique challenges and barriers to accessing safety resources and support. The relationship between self-efficacy, social media, and socio-economic status is complex, and further research is needed to fully understand its impact on school safety awareness.

It was recommended that:

1. There is a need to promote digital literacy to educate students, teachers, and parents on the safe and effective use of social media to promote school safety awareness.
2. School should implement programs and interventions aimed at enhancing students' self-efficacy, such as skills training and mentorship initiatives on transiting students on safety awareness creation in the school.
3. Provide targeted support and resources to students from lower socio-economic backgrounds to ensure equal access to safety resources and opportunities.
4. Foster a sense of community and social support among students, teachers, and parents to promote a safe and supportive learning environment

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